

Study of TiO₂ Nanoparticles as Lubricant Additive in Two-Axial Groove Journal Bearing

K. Yathish, K. G. Binu, B. S. Shenoy, D. S. Rao, R. Pai

Abstract—Load carrying capacity of an oil lubricated two-axial groove journal bearing is simulated by taking into account the viscosity variations in lubricant due to the addition of TiO₂ nanoparticles as lubricant additive. Shear viscosities of TiO₂ nanoparticle dispersions in oil are measured for various nanoparticle additive concentrations. The viscosity model derived from the experimental viscosities is employed in a modified Reynolds equation to obtain the pressure profiles and load carrying capacity of two-axial groove journal bearing. Results reveal an increase in load carrying capacity of bearings operating on nanoparticle dispersions as compared to plain oil.

Keywords—Journal bearing, TiO₂ nanoparticles, viscosity model, Reynolds equation, load carrying capacity.

I. INTRODUCTION

LUBRICANT additives play a major role in improving the tribological properties of modern day lubricants. Considering present day energy scenario and the ever increasing severity in operating conditions of machineries, it is imperative that we develop better tribological practices leading to reduced losses due to friction and wear. Journal bearings, being the more popular support mechanism in high speed applications, have been the focus of research for many tribologists. In addition to research on geometrical aspects of the sleeve, such as, externally adjustable pad bearings [1]–[3], thrust is also on promoting load capacity of journal bearings using improved lubricants.

The use of nanoparticles as lubricant additive has been a major subject of research in the past decade. Various metals and metal oxide nanoparticles have been studied as lubricant additives in thin film lubrication [4]–[11]. These studies have reported reduced friction and wear in tribo-surfaces with the use of nanoparticle lubricant additives. However, the application of nanoparticles in hydrodynamic lubrication is not clearly understood and represents a major gap in research. Nair et al. [12] and Shenoy et al. [13] obtained performance characteristics of fluid film bearings based on the viscosity

results provided by Wu et al. [14] and reported an increase in load carrying capacity. The above listed studies had considered only single nanoparticle concentration for obtaining the performance characteristics. The effect of viscosity variations with increasing nanoparticle concentrations needs to be studied. Viscosity of colloidal dispersions has been studied and modeled over the past many decades. The first viscosity model for dilute concentrations ($\phi = 0.01$) of spherical particles was provided by Einstein [15] in 1956 and is expressed as:

$$\bar{\mu} = \frac{\mu_{ps}}{\mu_{bf}} = 1 + 2.5\phi \quad (1)$$

The applicability of Einstein's equation was extended by Brinkman [16] to cover moderate particle concentrations as:

$$\bar{\mu} = \frac{\mu_{ps}}{\mu_{bf}} = \frac{1}{(1 - \phi)^{2.5}} \quad (2)$$

A more general viscosity model was later developed by Batchelor [17] by considering the particle interactions as:

$$\bar{\mu} = \frac{\mu_{ps}}{\mu_{bf}} = 1 + 2.5\phi + 6.5\phi^2 \quad (3)$$

These classical viscosity models were developed primarily for micrometer sized particle dispersions in base fluids. Their applicability to nanoparticle dispersions was studied by Kole et al. [18], who reported that for CuO nanoparticles in gear oil, these classical viscosity models severely underpredict viscosity variations with increasing particle volume fractions.

In this study, TiO₂ nanoparticle suspensions were formulated with low volume fractions in engine oil using two-step method. Their dynamic viscosities were experimentally measured using rheometer. From the measured viscosities, a mathematical model is derived based on assumed linearity of shear viscosity with volume fraction. The obtained viscosity model is then employed to predict shear viscosities at various volume fractions. The predicted viscosities are then used in the computations of load carrying capacity of two-axial groove journal bearing. The classical Reynolds equation for fluid film lubrication is modified to incorporate relative viscosities of nanoparticle dispersions. The modified equation is solved numerically using finite difference scheme to obtain the pressure profiles for various volume fractions of TiO₂

K. Yathish is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Mechanical Engineering at St Joseph Engineering College, Mangalore – 575 028, Karnataka – India (e-mail: yathsa2k@gmail.com)

K.G. Binu is an Associate Professor in the Department of Mechanical Engineering at St Joseph Engineering College, Mangalore – 575 028, Karnataka – India. (Corresponding author- phone: +91 824 2263753; fax: +91 824 2263751; e-mail: binuk@sjec.ac.in)

B.S. Shenoy is a Professor in the Aeronautical Department at Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal – 576 104 Karnataka, India (e-mail: sathishshenoyb@yahoo.com).

D.S. Rao and R. Pai are Professors in the Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering Department at Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal – 576 104 Karnataka, India (e-mail: dassrao@yahoo.com, rbpai@yahoo.com).

nanoparticle dispersions. The load carrying capacity is then computed and compared with results for plain oil.

II. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. Materials

TiO₂ nanoparticles used in this study were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The purchased TiO₂ nanoparticles were a mixture of rutile and anatase phase with primary particle size of < 100 nm (BET). The reasons for selecting TiO₂ nanoparticles are: a) TiO₂ nanoparticles are chemically stable and hence will not react with base fluid and tribo-surfaces at lubricating temperatures. b) TiO₂ nanoparticles are easily available, and c) TiO₂ nanoparticles are safe for human handling. The base fluid used in the formulation of nano-oil is engine oil (SAE 30) of viscosity 0.1078 Pa-s at 40 °C. Oleic acid was used as surfactant in the formulation of stable nanolubricants. The selection of Oleic acid as surfactant was on the basis of a separate dispersion stability analysis carried out by the authors.

B. Characterization of TiO₂ Nanoparticles

The morphology and chemical composition of purchased TiO₂ nanoparticles were characterized by TEM analysis with EDX. FT-IR spectrum of TiO₂ nanoparticles is also presented.

C. Formulation of TiO₂ Based Nanolubricant

The nanolubricant was formulated using the two-step approach. The purchased TiO₂ nanoparticles were subjected to an acid treatment process to remove the silica coating for better dispersion stability [19]. The processed TiO₂ nanoparticles were dispersed in engine oil using ultrasonication along with specified concentration of surfactant to prevent aggregation. A combination of direct (25 kHz frequency) and indirect sonication (33 kHz frequency) was used at 39% amplitude with a pulse interval of 10:2 for an optimized duration. Oleic acid was used as surfactant at an optimum concentration subject to TiO₂ nanoparticle concentration and base fluid considered.

D. Shear Viscosity Analysis

Stable dispersions of TiO₂ nanoparticles in engine oil was obtained at low concentrations ranging from 0.05 wt. % to 2.5 wt. % using the formulation approach mentioned in Section II C. The prepared samples were then subjected to shear viscosity measurements using a rotational rheometer. Shear viscosity variations due to varying concentrations as well as varying temperatures were studied. Temperatures were varied from 20°C to 80°C in steps of 10°C. The shear rate was kept constant at 40 per second.

III. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

A. Governing Equations for Journal Bearing

The classical two-dimensional Reynolds equation for hydrodynamic lubrication is expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(h^3 \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(h^3 \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \right) = 6\mu u \frac{dh}{dx} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is numerically solved to obtain the pressure distribution within the oil film developed in the clearance between bearing and journal. Integrating the pressures over the bearing area leads to load carrying capacity of the bearing.

Physical configuration of the two-axial groove journal bearing along with the coordinates is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Axial grooved Journal bearing configuration

In a plain journal bearing, the coordinate θ in the circumferential direction is taken from the position of maximum film thickness. In case of a grooved bearing shown in Fig. 1, this position needs to be found beforehand. This is done by assuming an arbitrary value of attitude angle ψ and the coordinate θ is measured from the vertical position. Using this arbitrary angle ψ , the lubricant film thickness in journal bearing is given by:

$$h = C \left(1 + \varepsilon \cos(\theta^* - \psi) \right) \quad (6)$$

The following dimensionless parameters are used to obtain the non-dimensional forms of (5) and (6):

$$\text{Angular coordinate } \theta = \frac{x}{R}; \quad \text{Axial coordinate } \bar{z} = \frac{z}{L};$$

$$\text{Bearing length to width ratio } \lambda = \frac{L}{D};$$

$$\text{Dimensionless film thickness } \bar{h} = \frac{h}{C};$$

$$\text{Dimensionless pressure } \bar{p} = \frac{pC^2}{\mu u R};$$

$$\text{Eccentricity ratio } \varepsilon = \frac{e}{C}; \quad \text{and}$$

$$\text{Non-dimensional relative viscosity } \bar{\mu} = \frac{\mu_{ps}}{\mu_{bf}}$$

where, μ_{ps} is the viscosity of nanoparticle suspension in oil and μ_{bf} is the viscosity of base fluid.

The non-dimensional Reynolds equation thus obtained is of the form,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left[\bar{h}^3 \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \theta} \right] + \left(\frac{R^2}{L^2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}} \left[\bar{h}^3 \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \bar{z}} \right] = 6\bar{\mu} \frac{\partial \bar{h}}{\partial \theta} \quad (7)$$

where, the non-dimensional film thickness is expressed as

$$\bar{h} = \frac{h}{C} = 1 + \varepsilon \cos(\theta^* - \psi) \quad (8)$$

B. Solution Scheme

The non-dimensional Reynolds equation, presented as (7), is solved numerically using finite difference method. The standard Reynolds boundary conditions are used in the solution scheme in which the negative pressures arising due to cavitation are neglected. The pressures at the ends of the bearing are also equated to zero, except for groove nodes. The pre-set non-dimensional groove pressure for a finite bearing is provided by Stachowiak [20] as $\bar{p} = 0.2$. The boundary conditions could then be expressed as,

$$\bar{p} = 0.2 \text{ at } \bar{z} = 0 \text{ and } \bar{z} = 1 \text{ at the grooves [20]}$$

$\bar{p} = 0$ at $\bar{z} = 0$ and $\bar{z} = 1$, for all nodes other than nodes in the grooves.

The boundary conditions as applied to the journal bearing are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Illustration of Reynolds boundary condition applied to grooved journal bearing

Central difference scheme is employed in discretizing the equation and Gauss-Siedel with SOR method is employed for numerical solution. MATLAB codes were developed for the computations. A rectangular grid is employed in the central difference scheme. The generated mesh of the bearing area with 130 (circumferential) \times 22 (axial) nodes used in the

computations is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 3 also shows the node numbers for both the axial grooves.

C. Nanofluid Viscosity Model

Stable TiO₂ dispersions in engine oil were prepared using procedure explained in section II C at TiO₂ volume fractions ranging from 0.0001 to 0.005 (0.05 wt. % to 2.5 wt. %). Fig. 4 shows the variation in experimental shear viscosity of TiO₂ dispersions in engine oil with increasing TiO₂ concentrations expressed in volume fraction ϕ .

Fig. 3 Mesh size and groove nodes

Fig. 4 shows the variation in experimental shear viscosity of TiO₂ dispersions in engine oil with increasing TiO₂ concentrations expressed in volume fraction ϕ . The linear trend line equation for the viscosity variation is obtained as:

$$\mu_{ps} = 8.4851\phi + 0.2189 \quad (9)$$

The above equation is employed in the numerical solution of modified Reynolds equation to simulate the relative viscosity $\bar{\mu}$ at different TiO₂ concentrations.

Fig. 4 Shear viscosity of TiO₂ nanolubricant as a function of TiO₂ volume fraction

D. Load Carrying Capacity

The load carrying capacity of the journal bearing is obtained by integrating the pressures across the bearing area. The integration is performed numerically using Simpson's 1/3 rule.

The non-dimensional load components along the line of centers and its perpendicular directions are obtained as:

$$\overline{W}_o = \frac{W_o C^2}{\mu U L R^2} = -R \int_0^1 \int_0^{2\pi} p \cos(\theta^* - \psi) d\theta d\bar{z} \quad (10)$$

$$\overline{W}_{\pi/2} = \frac{W_{\pi/2} C^2}{\mu U L R^2} = -R \int_0^1 \int_0^{2\pi} p \sin(\theta^* - \psi) d\theta d\bar{z} \quad (11)$$

The non-dimensional load capacity is then obtained as

$$\overline{W} = \sqrt{\overline{W}_o^2 + \overline{W}_{\pi/2}^2} \quad (12)$$

The attitude angle is calculated as $\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\overline{W}_o}{\overline{W}_{\pi/2}} \right)$

The load capacities are evaluated for different volume fractions of TiO₂ nanoparticles and compared with non-dimensional load for plain engine oil.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Validation of Computational Code

The computational code developed in MATLAB to solve the non-dimensional Reynolds equation for a two-axial groove journal bearing is validated by comparing the attitude angle and Sommerfeld number obtained from the code with the published results of Pinkus [21]. Table I presents a comparison of computed results with published results of Pinkus [21].

TABLE I
 VALIDATION OF COMPUTATIONAL CODE

Eccentricity ratio	Attitude angle		Sommerfeld number	
	Code	Pinkus [21]	Code	Pinkus [21]
0.2	64	63.968	0.714	0.6837
0.4	53	51.649	0.275	0.2843
0.4	45	42.588	0.125	0.1302
0.6	28	29.648	0.041	0.0462
0.8	22	22.887	0.019	0.0188
0.9	64	63.968	0.714	0.6837

From Table I, it can be observed that the computed results from the MATLAB code are in good agreement with the published results of Pinkus [21].

The validated code is used in calculating the hydrodynamic pressures for two-axial groove journal bearings operating on TiO₂ based nanolubricant samples. A sample relative pressure distribution across the bearing area is presented in Fig. 5 for TiO₂ nanoparticle concentration $\phi = 0.03$ and eccentricity ratio $\varepsilon = 0.7$.

Fig. 5 Pressure distribution for $\phi = 0.03$ and $\varepsilon = 0.7$

B. Characterization of Nanoparticles

The morphology and chemical characterization of purchased nanoparticles are carried out using TEM and related EDX analysis. Fig. 6 shows the TEM micrograph and the acquired EDX spectrum.

As seen from Fig. 6, the purchased nanoparticles have formed aggregates of size ~ 250 nm. The aggregates are nearly spherical in shape. The EDX spectrum confirms the chemical composition of TiO₂. The EDX also reveals the presence of silica coating on the nanoparticles.

C. Viscosity Analysis

Experimental viscosity analysis of the prepared nanolubricant samples reveals an increasing trend in viscosity of engine oil due to the addition of TiO₂ nanoparticle additives. Fig. 7 presents the viscosity variations at different TiO₂ concentrations and temperatures obtained using rotational rheometer as explained in section II D. It is observed from Fig. 7 that, the increase in viscosity with additive concentration is more significant at low temperatures and less influential at higher temperatures.

Fig. 6 TEM image of purchased TiO₂ nanoparticles along with EDX spectrum

Fig. 7 Experimental shear viscosities at different TiO_2 concentrations and temperatures

The viscosity variation with additive concentration has been linearly modeled for various TiO_2 concentrations at 30 °C and the linear trend line is presented in Fig. 4. Even though the experimental viscosities exhibit scatter, linear trend line is in fairly good agreement with the measured viscosities.

The experimentally obtained viscosities are compared with simulated viscosities using the classical models described in Section I (1 to 3). The comparison is presented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Comparison of viscosity models with experimental viscosities

As seen in Fig. 8, classical viscosity models (1 to 3) are found to severely underpredict the viscosities for nanoparticle dispersions. At the low volume fractions of additives considered, the classical models show negligible variation in viscosity. Hence, this study uses the linear trend line (9) obtained for experimental viscosities to simulate viscosities of TiO_2 nanolubricant samples for hydrodynamic bearing analysis.

D. Hydrodynamic Pressure Profiles

Fig. 9 compares relative non-dimensional pressures at the bearing mid-plane for different additive concentrations. The ratio of non-dimensional pressure to maximum pressure was obtained for an eccentricity ratio of $\varepsilon = 0.7$ and additive concentrations ranging from 0.001 to 0.05.

Fig. 9 Comparison of non-dimensional pressures for different TiO_2 nanoparticle concentrations at an eccentricity ratio of $\varepsilon = 0.7$

As seen in Fig. 9, the non-dimensional pressures increase with increasing TiO_2 nanoparticle concentrations. This increase in hydrodynamic pressures could be attributed to increase in viscosities of corresponding TiO_2 nanolubricant samples. Fig. 10 provides a comparison of resultant load carrying capacities for increasing TiO_2 nanoparticle concentrations.

Fig. 10 Comparison of load carrying capacities at different TiO_2 nanoparticle concentrations at

As seen in Fig. 10, load carrying capacities increases with increasing TiO_2 nanoparticle concentrations. It is observed that for a very low additive volume fraction of 0.001, the load carrying capacity is found to increase by only 4%. However, at increasing additive volume fraction of 0.01, the load

carrying capacity increases by 38% in comparison to plain engine oil.

The increase in hydrodynamic pressures and corresponding increase in load carrying capacity observed in Figs. 9 and 10 should however, be viewed in relation to viscosity variations with both, volume fractions and temperatures. As seen in Fig. 7, at high temperatures ($> 80^{\circ}\text{C}$), the influence of nanoparticles on viscosity of base lubricant is negligible. This could mean that, at higher temperatures usually observed in journal bearings subject to continuous operation at high loads, the viscosity variations due to nanoparticle additive might not result in significant improvement in load carrying capacity. However, the presence of nanoparticles will definitely aid in improving load carrying capacity at lower temperatures, especially during start-up, where journal bearings usually experience surface contact and wear. The influence of particle size on viscosities and bearing performance also, needs to be studied.

V. CONCLUSION

A novel approach of studying the influence of nanoparticle lubricant additives on load carrying capacity of journal bearings is presented. The presence of 0.01 volume fraction of TiO_2 nanoparticles in engine oil was found to increase the load carrying capacity by 38%. However, this increase in load capacity should be experimentally validated. The effect of additive particle size on the bearing performance also needs to be investigated.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. S. Shenoy and R. Pai, "Stability characteristics of an externally adjustable fluid film bearing in the laminar and turbulent regimes," *Trib. Int.*, vol. 43, pp. 1751-1759, 2010.
- [2] D. S. Rao, B. S. Shenoy, R. S. Pai, and R. Pai, "Stability of tri-taper journal bearings under dynamic load using a non-linear transient method," *Trib. Int.*, vol. 43, pp. 1584-1591, 2010.
- [3] B. S. Shenoy and R. Pai, "Effect of turbulence on the static performance of a misaligned externally adjustable fluid film bearing lubricated with couple stress fluids," *Trib. Int.*, vol. 44, no. 12, pp. 1774-1781, Jan. 2011.
- [4] B. Li, X. Wang, W. Liu, and Q. Xue, "Tribochemistry and antiwear mechanism of organic-inorganic nanoparticles as lubricant additives," *Tribol. Lett.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 79-84, 2006.
- [5] D. X. Peng, Y. Kang, R. M. Hwang, S. S. Shyr, and Y. P. Chang, "Tribological properties of diamond and SiO_2 nanoparticles added in paraffin," *Trib. Int.*, vol. 42, pp. 911-917, 2009.
- [6] M. Mosleh, N. D. Atnafu, J. H. Belk, and O. M. Nobles, "Modification of sheet metal forming fluids with dispersed nanoparticles for improved lubrication," *Wear*, vol. 267, pp. 1220-1225, 2009.
- [7] W. Li, S. Zheng, B. Cao, and S. Ma, "Friction and wear properties of $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{SiO}_2$ composite nanoparticles," *J. Nanopart. Res.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 2129-2137, 2011.
- [8] A. H. Battez, R. Gonzalez, D. Felgueroso, J. E. Fernandez, M. R. Fernandez, M. A. Garcia, et al., "Wear prevention behaviour of nanoparticle suspension under extreme pressure conditions," *Wear*, vol. 263, pp. 1568-1574, 2007.
- [9] L. Joly-Pottuz, B. Vacher, T. L. Mogne, J. M. Martin, T. Mieno, C. N. He, et al., "The role of Nickel in Ni-containing nanotubes and onions as lubricant additives," *Tribol. Lett.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 213-219, 2008.
- [10] E. F. Rico, I. Minondo, and D. G. Cuervo, "The effectiveness of PTFE nanoparticle powder as an EP additive to mineral base oils," *Wear*, vol. 262, pp. 1399-1406, 2007.
- [11] Y. Peng, Y. Hu, and H. Wang, "Tribological behaviors of surfactant-functionalized carbon nanotubes as lubricant additive in water," *Tribol. Lett.*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 247-253, 2007.
- [12] K. P. Nair, M. S. Ahmed, and S. T. Al-qahtani, "Static and dynamic analysis of hydrodynamic journal bearing operating under nano lubricants," *Int. J. Nanoparticles*, vol. 2, pp. 251-262, 2009.
- [13] B. S. Shenoy, K. G. Binu, R. Pai, D. S. Rao, and R. S. Pai, "Effect of nanoparticles additives on the performance of an externally adjustable fluid film bearing," *Trib. Int.*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 38-42, 2012.
- [14] Y. Y. Wu, W.C. Tsui, and T. C. Liu, "Experimental analysis of tribological properties of lubricating oils with nanoparticle additives," *Wear*, vol. 262, pp. 819-825, 2007.
- [15] A. Einstein, *Investigations on the theory of the Brownian movement*. New York: Dover Publications Inc., 1956.
- [16] H. C. Brinkman, "The viscosity of concentrated suspensions and solution," *J. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 20, pp. 571-581, 1952.
- [17] G. K. Batchelor, "The effect of Brownian motion on the bulk stress in a suspension of spherical particles," *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 83, pp. 97-117, 1977.
- [18] M. Kole and T. K. Dey, "Effect of aggregation on the viscosity of copper oxide – gear oil nanofluids," *Int. J. Therm. Sci.*, vol. 50, no. 9, pp. 1741-1747, 2011.
- [19] C.C. Li, S. J. Chang, and M. Y. Tai, "Surface chemistry and dispersion property of TiO_2 nanoparticles," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 93, no. 12, pp. 4008-4010, 2010.
- [20] G. Stachowiak and A. Batchelor, *Engineering Tribology*. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2013, ch. 5.
- [21] O. Pinkus O and B. Sternlicht, *Theory of Hydrodynamic Lubrication*. New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc., 1961.

Yathish Kumar K was born and brought up in Someshwar, Mangalore. He completed his graduation in Mechanical Engineering from University Visvesvaraya College of Engineering – Bangalore. He then completed his post graduation (M.Tech.) in Computational Analysis in Mechanical Sciences from St Joseph Engineering College, Mangalore in the year 2014.

Yathish is currently working as an Assistant Professor in the Department of Mechanical Engineering at St Joseph Engineering College – Mangalore. His areas of interest include, machine design, industrial tribology, and lubricant additives.

Binu K. Gopalakrishna was born and brought up in the town of Siddapur in Coorg District of Karnataka. He completed his graduation in Mechanical Engineering from PES College of Engineering – Mandya in the year 2000. His post-graduation (M.Tech) was in the field of Maintenance Engineering from Sri Jayachamarajendra College of Engineering – Mysore. He is currently pursuing his Doctoral degree in Tribology at Manipal Institute of Technology – Manipal.

Binu is currently working as an Associate Professor in the Department of Mechanical Engineering at St Joseph Engineering College – Vamanjoor, Mangalore. His areas of interest include: hydrodynamic lubrication, numerical analysis and related computations in MATLAB, nanoparticle science, colloidal stability, and rheology of multiphase fluids. He has 05 international journal publications to his credit.

Satish Shenoy B was born and brought up in Someswara, Mangalore. He finished his graduated in Mechanical Engineering in the year 1998 from Mysore University. He completed his M.Tech in Production Engineering and Systems Technology in 2001 from National Institute of Engineering, Mysore. He obtained his Doctoral Degree in 2009 from Manipal University in Tribology.

Shenoy is presently working as Professor in Department of Aeronautical and Automobile Engineering, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal University. His core expertise is in the domain of Computational Fluid Dynamics, Applied Numerical Methods, Aircraft Structures, Finite Element Methods, and Design of Manufacturing Tools. He has been the University topper during his PG entrance examination. He has more than 25 journal publication in the area of tribology to his credit.

D. Srikanth Rao was born and brought up in Agumbe, Karnataka. He finished his graduated in Mechanical Engineering in the year 1998 from Mysore University. He completed his M.Tech in Engineering Management in 1991 from Mangalore University. He obtained his Doctoral Degree in 2009

from Manipal University in the area of Tribology. His areas of interest include, Industrial Tribology, Manufacturing processes, Engineering Graphics, CAD CAM, Production Operations & Management, Essentials of Management, and Technology Management. He has several research publications in the area of tribology to his credit. Currently he is working as the Joint Director of Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal.

Raghuvir Pai. B born in Ballambat on 26/03/1964 had his Bachelors in Mechanical Engineering in 1982 from the University of Mysore. In 1988, he went to the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur and completed his Doctoral degree in Tribology. From February 1995 to February 1996, he had worked as a Department of Science and Technology (Government of India), BOYSCAST Postdoctoral research fellow at Cranfield University, England. He has research and teaching experience of 2 years (2000-2002) at Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, Australia.

Dr. Pai has published more than 100 research papers in Journals, International and National conferences. He has supervised 04 Ph.D. students in the area of Tribology Water Lubricated Bearings, Externally adjustable bearings and Tri-taper bearings and Tribology of machining metal matrix composites. He was a principal investigator for research projects by Philips, Bharat Heavy Electricals and GE JFWTC Global Research Centre, Bangalore. He has conducted more than 10 short courses in the field of Tribology. Currently he is heading Director-Research (Technical), Manipal University, Manipal.